

FP6-511678

ORCHESTRA

**Open Architecture and Spatial Data Infrastructure for
Risk Management**

Integrated Project

Priority 2.3.2.9 Improving Risk Management

WP3.6 – OA Service Implementation

**Implementation Specification of the Authorisation
Service**

Revision [1.0 / 1.3]

Document Control Page

Title	Implementation Specification of the Authorisation Service
Creator	Berlinghoff, Thomas Environmental Informatics Group
Subject	WP3.6 – OA Service Implementation
Description	This document defines a platform specific implementation specification of the Authorisation Service. The authorisation service is part of the ORCHESTRA UAA concept, and used in order to authorise principals to use operations of a service.
Publisher	ORCHESTRA consortium
Contributor	Berlinghoff, Thomas Environmental Informatics Group Ma, Wenjie Environmental Informatics Group
Date	2007-01-28
Type	Text
Format	application/msword
Identifier	http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=19464
Source	Not applicable
Language	en-GB.
Relation	None
Coverage	ORCHESTRA Consortium
Rights	
Deliverable number	D3.6.4
Work-Package contributing to the Deliverable	WP3.6
Contractual Date of Delivery	
Actual Date of Delivery	
Audience	<input type="checkbox"/> public <input type="checkbox"/> restricted <input type="checkbox"/> internal

Version number	1.0 / 1.3
Date	2007-12-11
Modified by	Ma, Wenjie Environmental Informatics Group
Comments	
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> WP leader accepted <input type="checkbox"/> SP leader accepted

	<input type="checkbox"/> Technical supervisor accepted <input type="checkbox"/> Quality checked <input type="checkbox"/> Project coordinator accepted
Action requested	<input type="checkbox"/> to be revised by partners involved in the preparation of the deliverable <input type="checkbox"/> for approval of the WP leader <input type="checkbox"/> for approval of the SP leader <input type="checkbox"/> for approval of the Technical Supervisor <input type="checkbox"/> for approval of the Quality Manager <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> for approval of the Project Coordinator Deadline for action: YYYY-MM-DD

Revision History

Revision	Date	Sections changed	Description
0.1 / 1.1	2006-08-15	All	Initial release
0.3 / 1.1	2006-10-08	4, Appendix B	- Added missing operations. - Added XML and WSDL documents
0.4 / 1.1	2006-10-19	4, 6.1.3, 6.1.4, 6.2	Incorporated changes made to the abstract specification
0.5 / 1.1	2006-10-24	6	Update of WSDL/XML documents.
0.6 / 1.1	2006-12-18	6, 7	Update of XML Schemas.
0.7 / 1.1	2007-01-18	All	Incorporate comments.
0.8 / 1.1	2007-01-28	Annex A	Updated WSDL and XML Schemas to reflect the new namespaces.
1.0 / 1.3	2007-12-11	All	Update new template

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i. Preface

The Authorisation Service is based on the abstract specification of the Authorisation Service, Version 1.2.

This implementation specification describes the implementation of the Authorisation Service with respect to the pilot requirements. This is a basic implementation of an role based Authorisation Service and supports permissions based on operations and time coverages.

For a detailed description of the Authorisation Service please refer to the correspondent abstract specification.

ii. Relations to the platform-neutral OA Service Specification

Derivations from the abstract service specification

The implementation specification of the Authorisation Service does not require derivations from the abstract specification to accommodate the technical contents of this document.

Modifications of the abstract service specification

Modifications of the abstract specification of the Authorisation Service are not necessary.

iii. Future work

Improvements in this document are desirable to consist of restrictions, such as the number of supported permission types as well as the usage of an authorisation context consisting of a simple sequence of key-value pairs. Further work will be put into the development of additional permission types (additional storage backends respectively), by implementing additional handlers, as well as additional authorisation contexts supporting more complex data structures. Support of further authorisation paradigms is also conceivable.

Implementation Specification of the Authorisation Service

1 Scope

This document defines an implementation specification of the Authorisation Service for the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform 1.1.1 and is based on the Template for the Implementation Specification of ORCHESTRA Services version 1.3. It specifies the interfaces implemented by the discussed service as well as their main purposes in relation to a concrete OSN. It provides a formal description of the implemented operations according to the rules defined in the specification of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform.

The current implementation follows a framework based approach including a reference implementation for all its components. According to the abstract specification it supports the assignment of permission to principals directly as well as a role based approach. Supported permission types and the storage backend used are aligned to the requirements of the pilot implementations. Therefore currently two permission types, an operation based and a time coverage based permission, are supported, using a MySQL database for storing their information.

Further versions may support usage of additional permission types (other storage devices respectively) by implementing correspondent handlers. For more information about developing handlers please refer to the UAA developers guide (“UAA Developers Guide 0.3”).

2 Conventions

2.1 UML Notation

All software engineering diagrams in this specification are presented using the Unified Modelling Language (UML) version 2.0 as the conceptual schema language.

2.2 Conformance

2.2.1 Conformance to the Platform and the OA

This implementation specification is conformant to the ORCHESTRA Meta-Model for Services (OMM-Service) and the specification of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform.

The data model defined in this document is compliant to the ORCHESTRA Meta-Model for Information (OMM-Info) and its platform specific representation.

The platform specific representation of the data model in XML Schema defined according to the rules of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform is ISO/DIS 19136 Geographic information - Geography Markup Language (GML) Version 2.1.2.

The following exception that is in compliance with platform rules apply:

1. Non-geographic Features (“normal classes”) are not derived from GML base types

The Web service specifications presented in this document are compliant to WSDL Version 1.1 with SOAP Version 1.1 HTTP binding.

The possible bindings are:

1. SOAP Version 1.1 HTTP binding

The binding is specified in chapter Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

The message style that shall be used is document/literal non-wrapped. This has the consequence that each operation takes only one single input parameter (an XML element). This XML element is referenced in the wsdl:message which has only one wsdl:part.

The mapping of an operation with multiple parameters to an operation with one single request parameter is subject to the chapter Mapping from an Abstract Specification.

2.2.2 Conformance to the abstract specification of the Authorisation Service

According to the conformance clause of the abstract specification of the Authorisation Service, this implementation specification can be considered conformant to the abstract specification.

The derivations from the abstract specification and from the mapping rules are documented in chapter Mapping from an Abstract Specification

2.3 Used parts of other documents

This document does not use significant parts of other documents.

3 Mapping from an Abstract Specification

The following subchapters defines the mapping between the abstract specification of the Authorisation Service and the platform specification for the “ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform”.

3.1 **Service Capabilities Interface**

The following table lists the mapping between operations of the Service Capabilities Interface:

Abstract Specification	Implementation Specification	Note
getCapabilities	getCapabilities	

Table 1: Mapping of operations of the Service Capabilities interface

The implementation specification of the Service Capabilities Interface is a 1:1 mapping from the abstract interface specification and is syntactically and semantically equivalent, except for service specific capabilities, to the specification of the Service Capabilities Interface.

The implementation specification of the Service Capabilities Interface does not follow strictly the mapping rules of the Platform Specification.

All operations of this interface have exactly 0 or 1 input parameter. A mapping of multiple operation parameters to one single request parameter as required by the document/literal message style is therefore not required.

3.1.1 **getCapabilities Operation**

This subchapter defines the mapping of the getCapabilities operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
request	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	O	request	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	M	(1)
return	OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse	M	return	OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse	M	(2)

Table 2: Mapping of parameters used by the getCapabilities operation

(1) The request parameter shall be mandatory in the implementation of the getCapabilities operation.

(2) Note that the type OA_CapabilitiesDocument of the abstract specification has been renamed to OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse for clarity.

3.1.1.1 **OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest Parameter Type**

This subchapter defines the mapping of the request parameter of the getCapabilities operation.

Attribute of Abstract Spec.			Parameter of Implementation Spec.			Note
acceptFormats	OA_MimeType[0..*]	O	acceptFormats	OA_MimeType[0..*]	O	(1)
acceptSpec Versions	CharacterString[0..*]	O	acceptSpec Versions	CharacterString[0..*]	O	
sections	OA_CapabilitiesSections	O	sections	OA_Capabilities Sections	O	

Table 3: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities request parameter

- (1) Independent of the contents of the acceptFormats attribute, the returned capabilities can always be formatted according to the default MIME type which is defined as “text/xml”.

3.1.1.2 OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse Parameter Type

This subchapter defines the mapping of the return parameter of the getCapabilities operation.

Attribute of Abstract Spec.			Parameter of Implementation Spec.			Note
capability Sections	Binary	M	capability Sections	xsd:anyType	M	(1)
format	OA_MimeType	M	format	OA_MimeType	M	(2)
schemaName	OA_CapabilitiesSchema	M	schemaName	OA_Capabilities Schema	M	
version	CharacterString	M	version	xsd:string	M	

Table 4: Mapping of attributes used in getCapabilities return parameter

- (1) The XML Schema type anyType is used in the implementation specification to allow the capabilities to be structured according to a certain XML Schema which is not predefined here. The capabilities shall be structured according to the schema indicated by the value of the schemaName attribute.
- (2) The value of the format attribute may always denote the default MIME Type “text/xml” indicating that the capabilities are formatted in XML.

3.1.1.3 OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities Parameter Type

Since OA_CapabilitiesDocument contains common service capabilities (OA_MI_ServiceCommonCapabilities) and service specific capabilities (OA_MI_ServiceSpecificCapabilities) this subchapter defines the mapping of the OA_MI_ServiceSpecificCapabilities.

Attribute of Abstract Spec.			Parameter of Implementation Spec.			Note
supportedPermissionTypes	OA_MI_PermissionType[1..*]	M	supportedPermissionTypes	xsd:enumeration	M	
supportedAuthorisationParadigms	OA_MI_AuthorisationParadigms[1..*]	M	supportedAuthorisationParadigms	xsd:enumeration	M	

supportedAdministrationInterfaces	OA_MI_AuthourisationParadigmas[1..*]	M	supportedAdministrationInterfaces	xsd:enumeration	M	
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Table 5: Mapping of attributes used in parameter OA_MI_Service_SpecificCapabilities

3.2 Authorisation Service Interface

The following table lists the mapping between operations of the Authorisation Service Interface:

Abstract Specification	Implementation Specification	Note
getCapabilites	getCapabilites	
authorise	authorise	
assignPermissionToPrincipal	assignPermissionToPrincipal	
unassignPermissionFromPrincipal	unassignPermissionFromPrincipal	
createRole	createRole	
deleteRole	deleteRole	
getRoles	getRoles	
updateRole	updateRole	
assignPermissionToRole	assignPermissionToRole	
unassignPermissionFromRole	unassignPermissionFromRole	
assignRoleToPrincipal	assignRoleToPrincipal	
unassignRoleFromPrincipal	unassignRoleFromPrincipal	
getPermissions	getPermissions	
getRoles	getRoles	

Table 6: Mapping of operations of the Authorisation Service interface

The implementation specification of the Authorisation Interface is a 1:1 mapping from the abstract interface specification and is syntactically and semantically equivalent to the specification of the Authorisation Interface.

3.2.1 authorise Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the authorise operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
authorisationContext	OA_AuthorisationContext	M	request	authoriseRequest	M	
response	CharacterString	M	response	xsd:string	M	

Table 7: Mapping of parameters used by the authorise operation

3.2.2 assignPermissionToPrincipal Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the assignPermissionToPrincipal operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
permission	OA_Permission	M	request	assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest	M	
principal	OA_Principal	M				

Table 8: Mapping of parameters used by the assignPermissionToPrincipal operation

3.2.3 unassignPermissionFromPrincipal Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the unassignPermissionFromPrincipal operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
permission	OA_Permission	M	request	unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequest	M	
principal	OA_Principal	M				

Table 9: Mapping of parameters used by the unassignPermissionFromPrincipal operation

3.2.4 getPermissions Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the getPermissions operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
query	OA_Query	O	request	getPermissionsRequest	M	

response	Sequence<OA_Permission>	M	response	SequenceOfOA_Permission	M	
----------	-------------------------	---	----------	-------------------------	---	--

Table 10: Mapping of parameters used by the getPermissions operation

3.2.5 createRole Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the createRole operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
role	OA_Role	M	request	createRoleRequest	M	

Table 11: Mapping of parameters used by the createRole operation

3.2.6 deleteRole Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the deleteRole operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
role	OA_Role	M	request	deleteRoleRequest	M	

Table 12: Mapping of parameters used by the deleteRole operation

3.2.7 getRoles Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the getRoles operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
query	OA_Query	O	request	getRolesRequest	M	
response	Sequence<OA_Role>	M	response	SequenceOfOA_Role	M	

Table 13: Mapping of parameters used by the getRoles operation

3.2.8 updateRole Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the updateRole operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
role	OA_Role	M	request	updateRoleRequest	M	

Table 14: Mapping of parameters used by the updateRole operation

3.2.9 assignPermissionToRole Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the assignPermissionToRole operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
role	OA_Role	M	request	assignPermission- ToRoleRequest	M	
Permission	OA_Permission	M				

Table 15: Mapping of parameters used by the assignPermissionToRole operation

3.2.10 unassignPermissionFromRole Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the unassignPermissionFromRole operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
role	OA_Role	M	request	unassignPermission- FromRoleRequest	M	
Permission	OA_Permission	M				

Table 16: Mapping of parameters used by the unassignPermissionFromRole operation

3.2.11 assignRoleToPrincipal Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the assignRoleToPrincipal operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
role	OA_Role	M	request	assignRoleToPrincipal- Request	M	
principal	OA_Principal	M				

Table 17: Mapping of parameters used by the assignRoleToPrincipal operation

3.2.12 unassignRoleFromPrincipal Operation

This subchapter defines the mapping of the unassignRoleFromPrincipal operation.

Parameter of Abstract Spec			Parameter of Implementation Spec			Note
role	OA_Role	M	request	unassignRoleFromPrincipalRequest	M	
principal	OA_Principal	M				

Table 18: Mapping of parameters used by the unassignRoleFromPrincipal operation

4 Platform-specific specification

4.1 Authorisation Service Overview

For a detailed description of the Authorisation Interface refer to the abstract specification of the Authorisation Service.

The following table lists the operations of the Authorisation Service and specifies whether they are adapted from another implementation specification.

Name	Overwrite
getCapabilites	Adapted from the specification of the OA Basic Service. Enhanced by service specific capabilities.
authorise	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
assignPermissionToPrincipal	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
unassignPermissionFromPrincipal	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
createRole	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
deleteRole	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
getRoles	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
updateRole	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
assignPermissionToRole	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
unassignPermissionFromRole	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
assignRoleToPrincipal	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
unassignRoleFromPrincipal	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
getPermissions	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.
getRoles	Copied from the specification of the Authorisation Service.

Table 19: Summary of Service Operations

The formal platform-specific description of the Authorisation Service can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

4.2 Specification of a Profile of Parameter Types used by the Authentication Service

The following data types are used within this specification:

Name	Usage	User Defined	from Profile
ServiceSpecificCapabilities	O	Yes	OA Basic Service
OA_AuthorisationContext	I	Yes	OA Types
OA_FeatureCollection	O	No	OA Types
OA_CapabilitiesDocument	O	No	OA MI Types
OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	I	No	OA Types
OA_InvalidParameterValue	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_MissingParameterValue	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_NoApplicableCode	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_InternalError	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types
OA_PermissionDeniedException	E	No	OA Types/Exception Types

Table 20: XML Types

The formal specification in XML of these types can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

This service specification does not define user defined Types.

4.3 Specification of the getCapabilities Operation

The mandatory getCapabilities operation informs the client of the capabilities of an ORCHESTRA Service Instance (OSI). This operation takes into account that in addition to capabilities that are common to all ORCHESTRA Services an ORCHESTRA Service may provide a specific set of capabilities. Furthermore, this operation allows the capabilities to be delivered according to different service meta-information schemas. This implementation specification therefore does not prescribe a certain schema to be used for the service capabilities. One or several schemas to be supported as well as a default schema have to be defined in the context of an OSN.

A service meta-information document is returned to the requesting client, either complete or including selected parts according to the given sections in the request.

A request to perform the getCapabilities operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 11. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional | mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although

some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	modified			
Overrides	not applicable			
Preconditions	none			
Post conditions	Service meta-information document returned to requesting client, either complete or including selected parts according to the given sections in the request			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest	mandatory	Specifies the parts of the meta-information to be returned. If absent, all parts shall be returned using the default schema.
Returns	Type		Description	
	OA_CapabilitiesDocument		Service capabilities of the specific OSI for the specific ORCHESTRA Service.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_VersionNegotiationFailed		List of versions in acceptSpecVersions parameter value in the getCapabilities request did not include any version supported by the OSI.	
	OA_UnsupportedSchema		The sections parameter in the getCapabilities request referred to a schema unsupported by the OSI.	

Table 21: Specification of the getCapabilities Operation

Note that in contrast to the abstract specification the request parameter is mandatory in order to simplify the mapping to the platform.

According to the abstract specification the request parameter consists of the following elements:

- acceptFormats: Optional parameter containing a prioritized sequence of zero or more re-

sponse formats desired by the caller, with preferred formats listed first. The formats are to be expressed in terms of MIME types. Independent of the contents of this element, the returned capabilities can always be formatted according to the default MIME type which is defined as “text/xml”.

- **acceptSpecVersions:** Optional parameter containing a prioritized sequence of zero or more specification versions of the ORCHESTRA service accepted by the client, with the preferred versions listed first. If no versions are included in the request, the highest version that the service supports shall be used.
- **sections:** Optional parameter specifying the schema for service meta-information according to which the capabilities shall be structured. In addition the names of requested sections in the complete set of meta-information elements can be listed. If absent, the complete service capabilities shall be returned structured according to a default schema which has to be defined in the context of an OSN.

According to the abstract specification the return parameter consists of the following elements:

- **capabilitySections:** Capabilities as meta-information document which is internally structured according to the indicated format and the indicated schema. It is either complete or includes only selected parts according to the given sections in the request.
- **format:** MIME type of the format in which the capabilities are returned as value of the capabilitySections parameter. The value of this attribute may always denote the default MIME Type “text/xml” indicating that the capabilities are formatted in XML.
- **schemaName:** Schema according to which the capabilities are returned. The value is the same as the one contained in the sections parameter of the request. If not explicitly included in the request, the value indicates the default schema.
- **version:** Version number of the specification to which the delivered service meta-information document is conform.

The formal platform-specific specification of the getCapabilities operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="getCapabilitiesRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="request" element="oab:OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getCapabilitiesResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="oab:OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse" />
</wsdl:message>
```

4.4 Specification of the authorise Operation

The mandatory authorise operation requests an authorisation decision for a given authorisation context.

A request to perform the authorise operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 22. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical
Overrides	Not applicable
Preconditions	none

Post conditions	none			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	authoriseRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_AuthorisationContextType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	authoriseResponse		Compliance value representing the advice how to treat a certain service request. Compliance values need to be agreed between a service and its Authorisation Service.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter.	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 22: Specification of the authorise Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the authorise operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="authoriseRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="authoriseRequest" element="author_requests:authoriseRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>

<wsdl:message name="authoriseResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="return" element="author_requests:authoriseResponse"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

4.5 Specification of the assignPermissionToRole Operation

The mandatory assignPermissionToRole operation assigns permission to a certain principal. Permission and principal have to exist already.

A request to perform the assignPermissionToRole operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 23. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	The specified role exists.			
Post conditions	The role has an additional permission, granting/revoking access to a certain resource.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	assignPermissionToRoleRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, OA_PermissionType and OA_RoleType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_RoleNotFoundException		The role to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionNotFoundException		The permission to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsException		There is already an association between the given principal and role.	

	OA_PermissionDeniedException	The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.
--	------------------------------	--

Table 23: Specification of the assignPermissionToRole Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the assignPermissionToRole operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="assignPermissionToRoleRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="assignPermissionToRoleRequest" element="author_requests:assignPermissionToRoleRequest" />
</wsdl:message>
```

4.6 Specification of the unassignPermissionFromPrincipal Operation

The mandatory unassignPermissionFromPrincipal operation removes a permission from a certain principal.

A request to perform the unassignPermissionFromPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 24. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	The principal exists and is currently associated with the specified permission.			
Post conditions	The permission is no longer associated with the principal.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, OA_PermissionType and OA_RoleType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the pa-	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing pa-	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		The principal to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionNotFoundException		The permission to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_NoSuchAssociationException		There is no association between the given principal and permission which could be deleted.	

	OA_PermissionDeniedException	The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.
--	------------------------------	--

Table 24: Specification of the unassignPermissionFromPrincipal Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the unassignPermissionFromPrincipal operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest" element="author_requests:unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

4.7 Specification of the createRole Operation

The mandatory createRole operation creates a new role. Newly created roles are empty. Neither permission nor principals are assigned, yet.

A request to perform the createRole operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 25. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	createRoleRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_RoleType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 25: Specification of the createRole Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the createRole operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="createRoleRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="createRoleRequest" element="author_requests:createRoleRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

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Specification of the createRole Operation

</wsdl:message>

4.8 Specification of the deleteRole Operation

The mandatory deleteRole operation deletes an existing role. Permission and principal assignments are deleted as well.

A request to perform the deleteRole operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 26. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	deleteRoleRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_RoleType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	Not applicable		Not applicable	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with in-	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_RoleNotFoundException		The role to be deleted cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 26: Specification of the deleteRole Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the deleteRole operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="deleteRoleRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="deleteRoleRequest" element="author_requests:deleteRoleRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

Implementation Specification of the Authorisation Service –
Specification of the deleteRole Operation

</wsdl:message>

4.9 Specification of the updateRole Operation

The mandatory updateRole operation updates an existing role, e.g. its description, etc.

A request to perform the updateRole operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 27. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	updateRoleRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_RoleType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with in-	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_RoleNotFoundException		Role to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 27: Specification of the updateRole Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the updateRole operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="updateRoleRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="updateRoleRequest" element="author_requests:updateRoleRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

Implementation Specification of the Authorisation Service –
Specification of the updateRole Operation

</wsdl:message>

4.10 Specification of the assignPermissionToPrincipal Operation

The mandatory assignPermissionToPrincipal operation assigns a permission to a certain role. Permission and principal have to exist already.

A request to perform the assignPermissionToPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 28. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, OA_PrincipalType and OA_PermissionType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter with invalid value.	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		Principal to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionNotFoundException		Permission to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsException		There is already an association between the given role and principal.	

	OA_PermissionDeniedException	The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.
--	------------------------------	--

Table 28: Specification of the assignPermissionToPrincipal Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the assignPermissionToPrincipal operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest"  
    element="author_requests:assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest" />  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.11 Specification of the unassignPermissionFromRole Operation

The mandatory unassignPermissionFromRole operation removes a permission from a certain role.

A request to perform the unassignPermissionFromRole operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 29. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	The specified role exists and is currently associated with the specified permission.			
Post conditions	The permission is no longer associated with the role.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, OA_RoleType and OA_PermissionType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the pa-	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing pa-	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_RoleNotFoundException		Role to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionNotFoundException		Permission to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_NoSuchAssociationException		There is no association between the given principal and the given role which could be deleted.	

	OA_PermissionDeniedException	The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.
--	------------------------------	--

Table 29: Specification of the unassignPermissionFromRole Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the unassignPermissionFromRole operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest"  
    element="author_requests:unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.12 Specification of the assignRoleToPrincipal Operation

Assigns an existing role to an existing principal. This indirectly assigns permissions associated with the role to the principal.

A request to perform the assignRoleToPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 30. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	assignRoleToPrincipalRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, OA_RoleType and OA_PrincipalType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_RoleNotFoundException		Role to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		Specified principal does not exist.	
	OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsException		The specified permission is already assigned to the principal.	

	OA_PermissionDeniedException	The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.
--	------------------------------	--

Table 30: Specification of the assignRoleToPrincipal Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the assignRoleToPrincipal operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="assignRoleToPrincipalRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="assignRoleToPrincipalRequest"  
    element="author_requests:assignRoleToPrincipalRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.13 Specification of the unassignRoleFromPrincipal Operation

Removes the given role from a certain principal. This indirectly removes permissions associated with the role from the principal.

A request to perform the unassignRoleFromPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 31. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	The principal is currently associated with the role.			
Post conditions	The principal is no longer associated with the role.			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	unassignRole-FromPrincipal-Request	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType, OA_RoleType and OA_PrincipalType.
Returns	Type		Description	
	None		None	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_RoleNotFoundException		Role to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		The specified principal does not exist.	
	OA_NoSuchAssociationException		There is no association between the given principal and the given role which could be deleted.	

	OA_PermissionDeniedException	The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.
--	------------------------------	--

Table 31: Specification of the unassignRoleFromPrincipal Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the unassignRoleFromPrincipal operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="unassignRoleFromPrincipalRequest">  
  <wsdl:part name="unassignRoleFromPrincipalRequest"  
    element="author_requests:unassignRoleFromPrincipalRequest"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

4.14 Specification of the getPermissions Operation

The mandatory getPermissions operation retrieves a list of permissions specified by a given query.

A request to perform the unassignRoleFromPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 32. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	getPermissionsRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_Query.
Returns	Type		Description	
	SequenceOfOA_Permission		Permissions matching the given query.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the pa-	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the miss-	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PrincipalNotFoundException		The principal to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionNotFoundException		The permission to act on cannot be found.	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation.	

Table 32: Specification of the getPermissions Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the getPermissions operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="getPermissionsRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="getPermissionsRequest"
    element="author_requests:getPermissionsRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getPermissionsResponse">
  <wsdl:part name="getPermissionsResponse"
    element="author_types:SequenceOfOA_Permission"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

4.15 Specification of the getRoles Operation

The mandatory getRoles operation retrieves an enumeration of existing roles.

A request to perform the unassignRoleFromPrincipal operation shall include the parameters listed and defined in Table 33. This table also specifies the data type (Type), the obligation [optional|mandatory] (Use) and a short description (Description) of each listed parameter. Furthermore the “Description” shall state the consequences for service instances if the correspondent parameter is optional and omitted. Although some values listed in the “Name” column appear to contain spaces, they shall not contain spaces.

Compliance	Identical			
Overrides	Not applicable			
Preconditions	None			
Post conditions	None			
Use	mandatory			
Receives	Name	Type	Use	Description
	request	getRolesRequest	mandatory	It contains the OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType and OA_Query.
Returns	Type		Description	
	SequenceOfOA_Role		Enumeration of OA_Role features.	
Throws	Type		Cause	
	OA_InvalidParameterValue		Operation request contains an invalid parameter value. Return the name of the parameter	
	OA_MissingParameterValue		Operation request does not include a parameter value. Return the name of the missing parameter	
	OA_NoApplicableCode		No other basic or service-specific exception type applies.	
	OA_InternalError		A problem occurred in the runtime environment (e.g. out of memory)	
	OA_PermissionDeniedException		The service requestor does not have permissions needed to perform the requested operation	

Table 33: Specification of the getRoles Operation

The formal platform-specific specification of the getRoles operation can be found in Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents.

```
<wsdl:message name="getRolesRequest">
  <wsdl:part name="getRolesRequest" element="author_requests:getRolesRequest"/>
</wsdl:message>
```

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```
<wsdl:message name="getRolesResponse">  
  <wsdl:part name="getRolesResponse" element="author_types:SequenceOfOA_Role"/>  
</wsdl:message>
```

5 Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents

5.1 XML Schema Documents

The following XML Schema Documents define the data types of this service.

The XML schema documents of the used data types are bundled in a zip file with the present document and can be downloaded at https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=20057.

In addition to XML Schema Documents specified in this appendix, this specification requires several normative XML Schema Documents. These XML Schema Documents define the common data types, e.g. common Exception Types, Basic Data Types and the GML Profile.

This file contains the XML Schema documents of the OA Basic Service and Authentication Service.

The namespaces

<http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0>,

<http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0>,

<http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0> are used.

5.1.1 authorisation_exceptions.xsd

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="windows-1252"?>
<schema xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
  xmlns:author_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/exceptions/1.0"
  xmlns:oab_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
  targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/exceptions/1.0"
  elementFormDefault="qualified"
  version="1.0">
  <element name="OA_PermissionDeniedException"
    type="author_exc:OA_PermissionDeniedExceptionType"
    substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException" />
  <complexType name="OA_PermissionDeniedExceptionType">
    <complexContent>
      <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
        <sequence />
      </extension>
    </complexContent>
  </complexType>
  <complexType name="OA_PermissionDeniedExceptionPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
      <element ref="author_exc:OA_PermissionDeniedException" />
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
  </complexType>
  <element name="OA_NoSuchAssociationException"
    type="author_exc:OA_NoSuchAssociationExceptionType" />
</schema>
```

```
        substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException" />
<complexType name="OA_NoSuchAssociationExceptionType">
    <complexContent>
        <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
            <sequence/>
        </extension>
    </complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_NoSuchAssociationExceptionPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
        <element ref="author_exc:OA_NoSuchAssociationException"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsException"
    type="author_exc:OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsExceptionType"
    substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException" />
<complexType name="OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsExceptionType">
    <complexContent>
        <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
            <sequence/>
        </extension>
    </complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsExceptionPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
        <element ref="author_exc:OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsException"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_PermissionNotFoundException"
    type="author_exc:OA_PermissionNotFoundExceptionType"
    substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException" />
<complexType name="OA_PermissionNotFoundExceptionType">
    <complexContent>
        <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
            <sequence/>
        </extension>
    </complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_PermissionNotFoundExceptionPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
        <element ref="author_exc:OA_PermissionNotFoundException"/>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
```

Implementation Specification of the Authorisation Service – Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents


```
        <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
    </complexType>
    <element name="OA_RoleNotFoundException"
        type="author_exc:OA_RoleNotFoundExceptionType"
        substitutionGroup="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException" />
    <complexType name="OA_RoleNotFoundExceptionType">
        <annotation>
            <documentation>
                Defined by the interface RbacAuthorisationAdministration at the
                AuthorisationService.
            </documentation>
        </annotation>
        <complexContent>
            <extension base="oab_exc:OA_AbstractException">
                <sequence/>
            </extension>
        </complexContent>
    </complexType>
    <complexType name="OA_RoleNotFoundExceptionPropertyType">
        <sequence minOccurs="0">
            <element ref="author_exc:OA_RoleNotFoundException" />
        </sequence>
        <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
    </complexType>
</schema>
```

5.1.2 authorisation_types.xsd

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="windows-1252"?>
<schema xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
  xmlns:author_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/types/1.0"
  xmlns:authen_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
  targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/types/1.0"
  elementFormDefault="qualified"
  version="1.0">
  <element name="OA_Permission" type="author_types:OA_PermissionType"/>
  <complexType name="OA_PermissionType">
    <annotation>
      <documentation>
        The abstract OA_Permission type is not used directly. Instead, concrete
        permissions have to inherit from OA_Permission.

        The boolean grant attribute indicates whether the permission grants
        (grant = true) or revokes (grant = false, default) access to the corresponding
        resource.
      </documentation>
    </annotation>
    <sequence>
      <element name="grant" type="boolean" default="false"/>
      <element name="service" type="string"/>
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <complexType name="OA_PermissionPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
      <element ref="author_types:OA_Permission"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink"/ -->
  </complexType>
  <element name="OA_TimeCoveragePermission"
    type="author_types:OA_TimeCoveragePermissionType"
    substitutionGroup="author_types:OA_OperationPermission"/>
  <complexType name="OA_TimeCoveragePermissionType">
    <complexContent>
      <extension base="author_types:OA_OperationPermissionType">
        <sequence>
          <element name="startTime" type="string"/>
          <element name="endTime" type="string"/>
        </sequence>
      </extension>
    </complexContent>
  </complexType>
</schema>
```

```
</extension>
</complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_TimeCoveragePermissionPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="author_types:OA_TimeCoveragePermission"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink"/ -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_AuthorisationContext" type="author_types:OA_AuthorisationContextType"/>
<complexType name="OA_AuthorisationContextType">
  <annotation>
    <documentation>
      The authenticatedPrincipal attribute contains an enumeration of
      OA_Principal features representing authenticated principals. The
      sourceService attribute contains the OA_OSI_Identifier of the service
      requesting an authorisation decision. This is important for Authorisa-
      tion
      Services serving multiple services.

      In order to support further Authorisation paradigms the
      OA_AuthorisationContext subtypes need to be created. Inherited
      authorisation contexts might include additional information needed by
      the
      authorisation paradigm. Especially for payment models this may include
      service statistics, e.g. number of requests, generated traffic, etc.
    </documentation>
  </annotation>
  <sequence>
    <element name="sourceService" type="string"/>
    <element name="authenticatedPrincipals">
      <complexType>
        <sequence>
          <element name="Sequence">
            <complexType>
              <sequence>
                <element name="element"
                  type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticatedPrincipalPropertyType"
                  minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
              </sequence>
            </complexType>
          </element>
        </sequence>
      </complexType>
    </element>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
```

```
        </element>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_AuthorisationContextPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
        <element ref="author_types:OA_AuthorisationContext"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink"/ -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_OperationPermission" type="author_types:OA_OperationPermissionType"
    substitutionGroup="author_types:OA_Permission"/>
<complexType name="OA_OperationPermissionType">
    <complexContent>
        <extension base="author_types:OA_PermissionType">
            <sequence>
                <element name="operationName" type="string"/>
            </sequence>
        </extension>
    </complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_OperationPermissionPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
        <element ref="author_types:OA_OperationPermission"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink"/ -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_KeyValueAuthorisationContext"
    substitutionGroup="author_types:OA_AuthorisationContext"
    type="author_types:OA_KeyValueAuthorisationContextType"/>
<complexType name="OA_KeyValueAuthorisationContextType">
    <complexContent>
        <extension base="author_types:OA_AuthorisationContextType">
            <sequence>
                <element name="context">
                    <complexType>
                        <sequence>
                            <element name="Sequence">
                                <complexType>
                                    <sequence>
                                        <element
                                            name="element"
                                            type="author_types:OA_KeyValuePairPropertyType"
                                            minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
                                    </sequence>
                                </complexType>
                            </element>
                        </sequence>
                    </complexType>
                </element>
            </sequence>
        </extension>
    </complexContent>
</complexType>
```

```
        </complexType>
    </element>
</sequence>
</complexType>
</element>
</sequence>
</extension>
</complexContent>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_KeyValueAuthorisationContextPropertyType">
    <sequence minOccurs="0">
        <element ref="author_types:OA_KeyValueAuthorisationContext"/>
    </sequence>
    <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_Role" type="author_types:OA_RoleType"/>
<complexType name="OA_RoleType">
    <annotation>
        <documentation>
            The OA_Role type represents a role consisting of a set of associated
            permissions.
            The attribute name contains the role?s name.
            The attribute description contains the role?s description.
            The attribute permissions contains a OA_FeatureCollection of
            OA_Permission features representing the permissions associated with
            the
            role.
        </documentation>
    </annotation>
    <sequence>
        <element name="name" type="string"/>
        <element name="description" type="string"/>
        <element name="permission">
            <complexType>
                <sequence>
                    <element name="Sequence">
                        <complexType>
                            <sequence>
                                <element name="element"
                                    type="author_types:OA_PermissionPropertyType"
                                    minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
                            </sequence>
                        </complexType>
                    </element>
                </sequence>
            </complexType>
        </element>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
</element>
```

```
        </sequence>
      </complexType>
    </element>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_RolePropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="author_types:OA_Role"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="OA_KeyValuePair" type="author_types:OA_KeyValuePairType"/>
<complexType name="OA_KeyValuePairType">
  <sequence>
    <element name="key" type="string"/>
    <element name="value" type="string"/>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="OA_KeyValuePairPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="author_types:OA_KeyValuePair"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
<element name="SequenceOfOA_Permission"
  type="author_types:SequenceOfOA_PermissionType"/>
<complexType name="SequenceOfOA_PermissionType">
  <sequence>
    <element name="Permissions">
      <complexType>
        <sequence>
          <element name="Sequence">
            <complexType>
              <sequence>
                <element name="Element"
                  type="author_types:OA_PermissionPropertyType"
                  minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded"/>
              </sequence>
            </complexType>
          </element>
        </sequence>
      </complexType>
    </element>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
</element>
</sequence>
```

```
</complexType>
<complexType name="SequenceOfOA_PermissionPropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="author_types:SequenceOfOA_Permission"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>

<element name="SequenceOfOA_Role" type="author_types:SequenceOfOA_RoleType"/>
<complexType name="SequenceOfOA_RoleType">
  <sequence>
    <element name="Roles">
      <complexType>
        <sequence>
          <element name="Sequence">
            <complexType>
              <sequence>
                <element name="Element"
                  type="author_types:OA_RolePropertyType"
                  minOccurs="0" maxOccurs="unbounded" />
              </sequence>
            </complexType>
          </element>
        </sequence>
      </complexType>
    </element>
  </sequence>
</complexType>
</element>
</sequence>
</complexType>
<complexType name="SequenceOfOA_RolePropertyType">
  <sequence minOccurs="0">
    <element ref="author_types:SequenceOfOA_Role"/>
  </sequence>
  <!-- attributeGroup ref="xlink:simpleLink" / -->
</complexType>
</schema>
```

5.1.3 authorisation_requests.xsd

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="windows-1252"?>
<schema xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
  xmlns:gml="http://www.opengis.net/gml"
  xmlns:author_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/types/1.0"
  xmlns:authen_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
  xmlns:author_requests="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/requests/1.0"
  xmlns:oab_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0"
  targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/requests/1.0"
  elementFormDefault="qualified"
  version="1.0">
  <element name="authoriseRequest" type="author_requests:authoriseRequest"/>
  <complexType name="authoriseRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInfo"
        type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
      <element name="authorisationContext"
        type="author_types:OA_AuthorisationContextType"/>
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <element name="authoriseResponse" type="author_requests:authoriseResponse"/>
  <complexType name="authoriseResponse">
    <sequence>
      <element name="compliance" type="string"/>
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <element name="createRoleRequest" type="author_requests:createRoleRequest"/>
  <complexType name="createRoleRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInfo"
        type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
      <element name="role" type="author_types:OA_RoleType"/>
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
  <element name="deleteRoleRequest" type="author_requests:deleteRoleRequest"/>
  <complexType name="deleteRoleRequest">
    <sequence>
      <element name="sessionInfo"
        type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
      <element name="role" type="author_types:OA_RoleType"/>
    </sequence>
  </complexType>
</schema>
```

```
<element name="assignPermissionToRoleRequest"
  type="author_requests:assignPermissionToRoleRequest" />
<complexType name="assignPermissionToRoleRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInfo"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
    <element name="oapermission" type="author_types:OA_PermissionType" />
    <element name="oarole" type="author_types:OA_RoleType" />
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest"
  type="author_requests:unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest" />
<complexType name="unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInfo"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
    <element name="oapermission" type="author_types:OA_PermissionType" />
    <element name="oarole" type="author_types:OA_RoleType" />
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="assignRoleToPrincipalRequest"
  type="author_requests:assignRoleToPrincipalRequest" />
<complexType name="assignRoleToPrincipalRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInfo"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
    <element name="oarole" type="author_types:OA_RoleType" />
    <element name="oapprincipa" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType" />
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="unassigneRoleFromPrincipalRequest"
  type="author_requests:unassigneRoleFromPrincipalRequest" />
<complexType name="unassigneRoleFromPrincipalRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInfo"
      type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType" />
    <element name="oarole" type="author_types:OA_RoleType" />
    <element name="oapprincipa" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType" />
  </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="updateRoleRequest" type="author_requests:updateRoleRequest" />
<complexType name="updateRoleRequest">
  <sequence>
    <element name="sessionInfo"
```

```
        type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
        <element name="oarole" type="author_types:OA_RoleType"/>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest"
    type="author_requests:assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest"/>
<complexType name="assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest">
    <sequence>
        <element name="sessionInfo"
            type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
        <element name="oapermission" type="author_types:OA_PermissionType"/>
        <element name="oaprincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequest"
    type="author_requests:unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequest"/>
<complexType name="unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequest">
    <sequence>
        <element name="sessionInfo"
            type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
        <element name="oapermission" type="author_types:OA_PermissionType"/>
        <element name="oaprincipal" type="authen_types:OA_PrincipalType"/>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="getPermissionsRequest" type="author_requests:getPermissionsRequest"/>
<complexType name="getPermissionsRequest">
    <sequence>
        <element name="sessionInfo"
            type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
        <element name="query" type="oab_types:OA_Query"/>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
<element name="getRolesRequest" type="author_requests:getRolesRequest"/>
<complexType name="getRolesRequest">
    <sequence>
        <element name="sessionInfo"
            type="authen_types:OA_AuthenticationSessionInformationType"/>
        <element name="query" type="oab_types:OA_Query"/>
    </sequence>
</complexType>
</schema>
```

5.2 WSDL Document

The following WSDL Version 1.1 document is the formal specification of the Authorisation Service according to rules of the “ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform”. It defines the mandatory SOAP binding.

The WSDL document is bundled in a zip file with the present document and can be downloaded at https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=20057.

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<!-- edited with XMLSpy v2007 (http://www.altova.com) by new (new.com) -->
<wsdl:definitions xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
    xmlns:soap="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/soap/"
    xmlns:http="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/http/"
    xmlns:mime="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/mime/"
    xmlns:wsdl="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/wsdl/"
    xmlns:author="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService"
    xmlns:author_oami="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/oami/1.0"
    xmlns:author_requests="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/requests/1.0"
    xmlns:author_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/exceptions/1.0"
    xmlns:author_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/types/1.0"
    xmlns:authen_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/exceptions/1.0"
    xmlns:oab_exc="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
    xmlns:oab_types="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0"
    xmlns:bdt="http://eu-orchestra.org/basicTypes/1.0"
    name="WSDLComponent1"
    targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService">
  <wsdl:types>
    <xs:schema targetNamespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService"
        xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
        elementFormDefault="qualified"
        attributeFormDefault="qualified">
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/basicTypes/1.0"
          schemaLocation="basic_types.xsd"/>
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/exceptions/1.0"
          schemaLocation="oa_basic_ex.xsd"/>
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/OABasicService/types/1.0"
          schemaLocation="oa_basic.xsd"/>
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/types/1.0"
          schemaLocation="authorisation_types.xsd"/>
      <xs:import namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/requests/1.0"
          schemaLocation="authorisation_requests.xsd"/>
    </xs:schema>
  </wsdl:types>
</wsdl:definitions>
```

Implementation Specification of the Authorisation Service – Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents


```
<xs:import
  namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthorisationService/exceptions/1.0"
  schemaLocation="authorisation_exceptions.xsd"/>
<xs:import
  namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/types/1.0"
  schemaLocation="authentication_types.xsd"/>
<xs:import
  namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/AuthenticationService/exceptions/1.0"
  schemaLocation="authentication_exceptions.xsd"/>
<xs:import
  namespace="http://eu-orchestra.org/OA/UserManagementService/types/1.0"
  schemaLocation="usermanagement_types.xsd"/>
</xs:schema>
</wSDL:types>
<wSDL:message name="getCapabilitiesRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="oaCapabilitiesRequest"
    element="oab_types:OA_GetCapabilitiesRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="getCapabilitiesResponse">
  <wSDL:part name="oaCapabilitiesResponse"
    element="oab_types:OA_GetCapabilitiesResponse"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="authoriseRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="authoriseRequest" element="author_requests:authoriseRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="authoriseResponse">
  <wSDL:part name="return" element="author_requests:authoriseResponse"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="createRoleRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="createRoleRequest" element="author_requests:createRoleRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="deleteRoleRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="deleteRoleRequest" element="author_requests:deleteRoleRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="assignPermissionToRoleRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="assignPermissionToRoleRequest"
    element="author_requests:assignPermissionToRoleRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest"
    element="author_requests:unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest"/>
</wSDL:message>
<wSDL:message name="assignRoleToPrincipalRequest">
  <wSDL:part name="assignRoleToPrincipalRequest"
```

```
        element="author_requests:assignRoleToPrincipalRequest" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="unassignRoleFromPrincipalRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="unassignRoleFromPrincipalRequest"
        element="author_requests:unassignRoleFromPrincipalRequest" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="updateRoleRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="updateRoleRequest" element="author_requests:updateRoleRequest" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest"
        element="author_requests:assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequest"
        element="author_requests:unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequest" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getPermissionsRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="getPermissionsRequest"
        element="author_requests:getPermissionsRequest" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getPermissionsResponse">
    <wsdl:part name="getPermissionsResponse"
        element="author_types:SequenceOfOA_Permission" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getRolesRequest">
    <wsdl:part name="getRolesRequest" element="author_requests:getRolesRequest" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="getRolesResponse">
    <wsdl:part name="getRolesResponse" element="author_types:SequenceOfOA_Role" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="InvalidParameterValueFault">
    <wsdl:part name="OA_InvalidParameterValue"
        element="oab_exc:OA_InvalidParameterValue" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="MissingParameterValueFault">
    <wsdl:part name="OA_MissingParameterValue"
        element="oab_exc:OA_MissingParameterValue" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="NoApplicableCodeFault">
    <wsdl:part name="OA_NoApplicableCode" element="oab_exc:OA_NoApplicableCode" />
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="InternalErrorFault">
    <wsdl:part name="OA_InternalError" element="oab_exc:OA_InternalError" />
```

Implementation Specification of the Authorisation Service – Appendix A: XML Schema and WSDL Documents


```
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="PrincipalNotFoundFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_PrincipalNotFoundException"
    element="authen_exc:OA_PrincipalNotFoundException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="PermissionNotFoundFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_PermissionNotFoundException"
    element="author_exc:OA_PermissionNotFoundException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="AssociationAlreadyExistsFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsException"
    element="author_exc:OA_AssociationAlreadyExistsException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="NoSuchAssociationFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_NoSuchAssociationException"
    element="author_exc:OA_NoSuchAssociationException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="RoleNotFoundFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_RoleNotFoundException"
    element="author_exc:OA_RoleNotFoundException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="PermissionDeniedFault">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_PermissionDeniedException"
    element="author_exc:OA_PermissionDeniedException"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="VersionNegotiationFailed">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_VersionNegotiationFailed"
    element="oab_exc:OA_VersionNegotiationFailed"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:message name="UnsupportedCapSchema">
  <wsdl:part name="OA_UnsupportedCapSchema"
    element="oab_exc:OA_UnsupportedCapSchema"/>
</wsdl:message>
<wsdl:portType name="AuthorisationService">
  <wsdl:operation name="getCapabilities">
    <wsdl:input name="capabilitiesRequest"
      message="author:getCapabilitiesRequest"/>
    <wsdl:output name="capabilitiesResponse"
      message="author:getCapabilitiesResponse"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
      message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
      message="author:MissingParameterValueFault"/>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault"/>
  </wsdl:operation>
</wsdl:portType>
</wsdl:binding>
</wsdl:service>
</wsdl:definitions>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
<wsdl:fault name="VersionNegotiationFailed"
  message="author:VersionNegotiationFailed" />
<wsdl:fault name="UnsupportedCapSchema"
  message="author:UnsupportedCapSchema" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="authorise">
  <wsdl:documentation>
    Requests an authorisation decision for a given authorisation con-text.
  </wsdl:documentation>
  <wsdl:input name="authoriseRequestRequest"
    message="author:authoriseRequest" />
  <wsdl:output name="authoriseRequestResponse"
    message="author:authoriseResponse" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
    message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="unassignPermissionFromPrincipal">
  <wsdl:input name="unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequestRequest"
    message="author:unassignPermissionFromPrincipalRequest" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
    message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="author:PrincipalNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound"
    message="author:PermissionNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoSuchAssociation"
    message="author:NoSuchAssociationFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="assignPermissionToPrincipal">
  <wsdl:input name="assignPermissionToPrincipalRequestRequest"
    message="author:assignPermissionToPrincipalRequest" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
```

```
        message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="author:PrincipalNotFoundFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound"
        message="author:PermissionNotFoundFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="AssociationAlreadyExists"
        message="author:AssociationAlreadyExistsFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updateRole">
    <wsdl:input name="updateRoleRequestRequest"
        message="author:updateRoleRequest" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
        message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
        message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound" message="author:RoleNotFoundFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="unassignRoleFromPrincipal">
    <wsdl:input name="unassignRoleFromPrincipalRequestRequest"
        message="author:unassignRoleFromPrincipalRequest" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
        message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
        message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="assignRoleToPrincipal">
    <wsdl:input name="assignRoleToPrincipalRequestRequest"
        message="author:assignRoleToPrincipalRequest" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
        message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
        message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound" message="author:RoleNotFoundFault" />
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="author:PrincipalNotFoundFault" />
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="AssociationAlreadyExists"
            message="author:AssociationAlreadyExistsFault" />
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="unassignPermissionFromRole">
  <wsdl:input name="unassignPermissionFromRoleRequestRequest"
             message="author:unassignPermissionFromRoleRequest" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
             message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
             message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound" message="author:RoleNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound"
             message="author:PermissionNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoSuchAssociation"
             message="author:NoSuchAssociationFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="assignPermissionToRole">
  <wsdl:input name="assignPermissionToRoleRequestRequest"
             message="author:assignPermissionToRoleRequest" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
             message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
             message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound" message="author:RoleNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound"
             message="author:PermissionNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="AssociationAlreadyExists"
             message="author:AssociationAlreadyExistsFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="deleteRole">
  <wsdl:input name="deleteRoleRequestRequest"
             message="author:deleteRoleRequest" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
             message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
             message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
<wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound" message="author:RoleNotFoundFault" />
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="createRole">
  <wsdl:input name="createRoleRequestRequest"
    message="author:createRoleRequest" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
    message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getPermissions">
  <wsdl:input name="getPermissionsRequestRequest"
    message="author:getPermissionsRequest" />
  <wsdl:output name="permission" message="author:getPermissionsResponse" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
    message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" message="author:PrincipalNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound"
    message="author:PermissionNotFoundFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoSuchAssociationException"
    message="author:NoSuchAssociationFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getRoles">
  <wsdl:input name="getRolesRequestRequest"
    message="author:getRolesRequest" />
  <wsdl:output name="return" message="author:getRolesResponse" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue"
    message="author:InvalidParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue"
    message="author:MissingParameterValueFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode" message="author:NoApplicableCodeFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError" message="author:InternalErrorFault" />
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied" message="author:PermissionDeniedFault" />
</wsdl:operation>
```

```
</wsdl:portType>
<wsdl:binding name="AuthorisationService" type="author:AuthorisationService">
  <soap:binding style="document" transport="http://schemas.xmlsoap.org/soap/http"/>
  <wsdl:operation name="getCapabilities">
    <soap:operation soapAction="getCapabilities" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
      <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
      <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
      <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
      <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
      <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
      <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="UnsupportedCapSchema">
      <soap:fault name="UnsupportedCapSchema" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="VersionNegotiationFailed">
      <soap:fault name="VersionNegotiationFailed" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
  </wsdl:operation>
  <wsdl:operation name="authorise">
    <wsdl:documentation>
      Requests an authorisation decision for a given authorisation con-text.
    </wsdl:documentation>
    <soap:operation soapAction="authorise" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
      <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
      <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
      <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="unassignPermissionFromPrincipal">
    <soap:operation soapAction="unassignPermissionFromPrincipal"
        style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoSuchAssociation">
        <soap:fault name="NoSuchAssociation" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
```

```
<wsdl:operation name="assignPermissionToPrincipal">
  <soap:operation soapAction="assignPermissionToPrincipal" style="document"/>
  <wsdl:input>
    <soap:body use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:input>
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionNotFound" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="AssociationAlreadyExists">
    <soap:fault name="AssociationAlreadyExists" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="updateRole">
  <soap:operation soapAction="updateRole" style="document"/>
  <wsdl:input>
    <soap:body use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:input>
  <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
  <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
  </wsdl:fault>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="RoleNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="unassignRoleFromPrincipal">
    <soap:operation soapAction="unassignRoleFromPrincipal" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="assignRoleToPrincipal">
    <soap:operation soapAction="assignRoleToPrincipal" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
```

```
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="RoleNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="AssociationAlreadyExists">
    <soap:fault name="AssociationAlreadyExists" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="unassignPermissionFromRole">
    <soap:operation soapAction="unassignPermissionFromRole" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="RoleNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoSuchAssociation">
        <soap:fault name="NoSuchAssociation" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
```

```
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="assignPermissionToRole">
    <soap:operation soapAction="assignPermissionToRole" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalServerError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalServerError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="RoleNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionNotFound" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="AssociationAlreadyExists">
        <soap:fault name="AssociationAlreadyExists" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="deleteRole">
    <soap:operation soapAction="deleteRole" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
```

```
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="RoleNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="RoleNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="createRole">
    <soap:operation soapAction="createRole" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getPermissions">
    <soap:operation soapAction="getPermissions" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
```

```
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
    <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
    <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
    <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PrincipalNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="PrincipalNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionNotFound">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionNotFound" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="NoSuchAssociationException">
    <soap:fault name="NoSuchAssociationException" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
<wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
    <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
</wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
<wsdl:operation name="getRoles">
    <soap:operation soapAction="getRoles" style="document"/>
    <wsdl:input>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:input>
    <wsdl:output>
        <soap:body use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:output>
    <wsdl:fault name="InvalidParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="InvalidParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="MissingParameterValue">
        <soap:fault name="MissingParameterValue" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="NoApplicableCode">
        <soap:fault name="NoApplicableCode" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="InternalError">
        <soap:fault name="InternalError" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
    <wsdl:fault name="PermissionDenied">
```

```
        <soap:fault name="PermissionDenied" use="literal"/>
    </wsdl:fault>
</wsdl:operation>
</wsdl:binding>
<wsdl:service name="AuthorisationService">
    <wsdl:port name="AuthorisationService" binding="author:AuthorisationService">
        <soap:address
            location="http://stl-d-pl1.htw-
            saarland.de:8080/axis2/services/AuthorisationService"/>
    </wsdl:port>
</wsdl:service>
</wsdl:definitions>
```

6 Appendix B: UML Model

6.1 Static model

6.2 Dynamic model

Assign a permission to a principal

Unassign a permission from a principal

